

THE IMPACT OF MANPOWER TRAINING ON STAFF DEVELOPMENT IN THE NIGERIAN PUBLIC SERVICE

JOHN OGHENEKEVWE IFAKA, PH.D¹

Department of Public Administration, College of Management and Social Sciences,
Samuel Adegboyega University. Ogwa, Edo State, Nigeria.

+2348064403142

ifaka29@gmail.com

and

JOSEPH UNUFE²,

Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Benin. Benin City, Nigeria.

+2347036647414

Abstract

The study is focused on the impact of manpower training on staff development in Nigerian Public Service. The objectives of the study are examine the relationship between training and organizational development and investigate the influence of training on organizational development. The study adopted survey method. The population of the study was 511 while the sample size was 220. The study utilized quantitative analyses. The study found that there is a positive and significant relationship between training and development. However, the study accounted that the strength of the relationship between training and development was weak in the public service. The study recommended there is the need to incorporate incentives into training programme as this will increase the motivation for organization that is strong.

Keywords: Human resources, Organizational Development, Performance and Training.

Introduction.

Organization requires manpower and contentious training to maximize efficiency. Improved employees' performance is a function of organization training and capabilit (Oribabor, 2000). A decisive factor that can change experienced by firms and public organizations is the investment in the human resources in the organization. The ability and strategy to effectively carry out proactive action in the face of competition and uncertainty is dependent on the quality of manpower training in public organization.

Armstrong (2012) noted that manpower planning is determining the required number of workmen (skilled and unskilled) needed for a certain type of work in a given industry. They form the bedrock of the organization that works toward achieving the aims and objectives of the organization. With the fluid nature of human organization and global dynamics confronting public organization that must continue to meeting public expectation, effective

training and management of manpower is now at the front burner of public administrator (Thomason, 2001). It is therefore necessary that an organization's manpower planning and training needs be devised in a way that dovetail into engendering solutions directed toward well-defined objectives and policies of public organization.

Statement of the Research Problem

Public organizations like other organization deployed available resources to achieve organizational goals and objectives. These resources include include Man, Money, Material, Maintenance and Machine. There is a general consensus that among human resources (man) is the most important resources and requires time to develop. Since the resources are relatively scarce, wastage and misuse of resources have to be avoided as much as possible. Efficient and effective use of human resources is therefore critical to organizational development. (Armstrong 2012).

A successful organization is one which has an effective human resources policy on ground. It is important to note that the task of managing resources is not an easy one especially when it comes to the management of people as resources. Since it is not easy managing people with individual differences and situating the growth and efficiency of all organization, adequate plans and strategies needs to be put in place which are aimed at acquiring the right personnel, and also fine turning that personnel to function optimally in the realization of organizational goals (Cole, 2002).

Previous studies have identified the role of training on organizational development but the impact of the role on public organization development is lacking. The problem here is to determine the quality of human capital development that will lead to improved performance and how these impact organizational development in the Nigerian Public service. Acquiring competent human resources for organization, may not provide the required output desired by organization; to fill in the void in the literature, the Researchers investigated the impact of manpower training on organizational development as a function of productivity.

Objectives of the Study

The research objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between training and organizational development
2. Investigate the influence of training on organizational development

Research Questions

From the research objectives, the following questions were drawn.

1. Is there relationship between training and organizational development?
2. Do training have impact on organizational development

Research Hypotheses

To guide this study, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no relationship between training and organizational development?
2. Training do no impact organizational development?

The Significance of the Study

In critical times like this when organizations are faced with uncertainties, the need for training to meet new challenges is resurfacing and taking the front burner of organizational quest to improve performance and develop its operation in all its ramifications. The significance of the study is therefore targeted at providing policy makers and management with quantitative evidence of the needs and importance of training to organization development.

Scope of the Study

This study examines the impact of manpower training on organizational development in the Nigerian Public service. The Nigeria Gas Company Warri, Delta State served as the case study.

Definition of terms

Human resources: Human resources is comprising of people who make up the workforce of an organization. They are the most vital asset of the organization. They are nominally described as human capital and is in relationship to the skills and knowledge set they possess to perform organization task in line with its sets goals and objectives. (Cole, 2002).

Organizational Development: this is the implementation of organizational policies and programmes in order to achieve organizational goals in relationship with changing circumstances. Since organization environment and factors are not statics, organization are regularly modified to new set of expectations that relates to adjusting its performance to meet with new demands, culture and technology.

Performance:

The measurement of actual output, results or total products against the expected or anticipated target. Organization performance is an indicator of the quality and quantity of the set of skills and organization allocate to specific task and the result or out produce at a given timeframe.

Training:

The acquisition of skills targeted at expanding the quality of a person or persons towards meeting or actualizing or performing a specific or wide range of tasks in an organization. It is also the further development of a person or group of persons' capacity to increase organization productivity as well as perform unique tasks or challenges confronting an organization.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework.

Human resources are the greatest asset of all resources in an organization, yet most problems facing organizations in modern time is the problem of human resources development and utilization for effective performance. Armstrong (2012) and Cole (2002) have both stressed that manpower development constitute the decisive factor in organizational development. Therefore, human resources, being the whole man, are more productive, most versatile and most resourceful, if he is properly used. This explains why the improvement of human effectiveness in work is the greatest opportunity for the improvement of performance and result. Brown (2002) and Noe and Tews (2008) identified among others, the development of human resources through training, experience and career planning as well as effective utilization of existing manpower as critical to improvement of performance.

Training in all ramification include the physically, socially, intellectually and mentally improvement necessary in facilitating productivity and the development of personnel as well as the development of organization and its capability (Cole, 2002; Armstrong, 2012).

Noe (2010) observed that staff training and development is a work activity that can make a very significant contribution to the overall effectiveness and profitability of an organization. He therefore, provides a systematic approach to training which encases the main elements of training.

The effectiveness and success of an organization therefore lies on the people who form and work within the organization. It follows therefore that the employees in an organization are deployed to perform their duties and make meaningful contributions to the success of the organizational goals. This requires the acquisition of the relevant skills and knowledge. In appreciation of this fact, organization conduct training and development programmes for the different levels of their manpower.

Training has been observed as part of human development. Human development is a process of increase people capacity to make informed choices. In principle, these choices can be infinite and change over time.

It is obvious that administrators cannot be successful without well skilled and well trained people. The importance of incorporating training into organizational or institutional role of staffing is manifested on the capacity to improve and develop organizational development.

The need for improved productivity in organization has become universally accepted and that it depends on efficient and effective training. It has further become necessary in view of advancement in modern world to invest in training. Absence of these programme often manifest tripartite problems of incompetence, inefficiency and ineffectiveness. Oribabor (2000) and Isyaku (2000) have both noted training and development aim at developing competences such as technical, human, conceptual and managerial for the furtherance of individual and organization growth.

Mathews, Ueno, Kekale, Repka, Pereira and Silva (2001) is of the opinion that the objectives of training are to: provide the skills, knowledge and aptitudes necessary to undertake required job efficiently develop the workers so that if he has the potentials, he may progress, increase efficiency by reducing spoiled work, misuse of machines and lessening physical risks.

Training and development requires understanding of all the changes that take place as a result of learning. As the generator of new knowledge, employee training and development is placed within a broader strategic context of human resources management. To preserve its obtained positions and increase competitive advantage, the organization needs to be able to create new knowledge, and not only to rely solely on utilization of the existing (Groot, Van and Brink, 2000).

Thus, the continuous employee training and development has a significant role in the development of individual and organizational performance. The strategic procedure of employee training and development needs to encourage creativity, ensure inventiveness and shape the entire organizational knowledge that provides the organization with uniqueness and differentiates it from the others. The survival of the organization is tied to employees needs to possess the required knowledge and capacity to solve certain problems (Tharenou, 2010)

Latif (2012) noted that employee training and development does not imply only obtaining new knowledge, abilities and skills, but also the possibility to promote entrepreneurship, introduce employees to changes, encourage the changes of their attitude, introduce the employees to important business decisions and involve them actively in the process of decision making. To precisely define expectations and attract skilled workforce, more and more employment advertisements offer a certain number of annual hours or days for education.

Similarly, Ehrhardt, Miller, Freeman and Hom (2011) acknowledged that the most wanted resources are the people with particular knowledge, skills and abilities. Managers must learn to manage them, and the organizations to employ and retain them. Knowledge based organizations must preserve their competitive advantage by retaining skilled workforce, workers of knowledge, strengthening their motivation and improving the reward and compensation systems according to the workers' performances.

Within the context of learning organization, it is not sufficient for the worker only to add value to the organization based on his knowledge, but he also has to receive knowledge. He gives as much knowledge as he receives. For the present day employees, the wage by itself is not a sufficient incentive, but they also need investment into themselves in a sense of investing in their knowledge. Employees no longer work for money alone, nor can they be influenced by traditional attractive financial packages; they also require self-development to add value to their profile (Cheung & Chan, 2012)

Training is the corner stone of sound management, for it makes employees more effective and productive. It is actively and intimately connected with all the personnel or managerial activities. It is an integral part of the whole management programme, with all its many activities functionally related (Salas & Cannon-Bowers, 2001).

Park and Jacobs (2011) expressed that training is a practical and vital necessity because, apart from the other advantages mentioned above, it enables employees to develop and rise within the organization, and increase their market value, earning power and job security. It molds the employee's attitudes and helps them to achieve a better cooperation with the company and a great loyalty to it. Training, moreover, heightens the morale of the employees, for it helps in reducing dissatisfaction, complaints, grievances and absenteeism, reduces the rate of turnover.

Ubeda-García, Marco-Lajara, Sabater-Sempere and García-Lillo (2013) maintained that trained employees make a better and economical use of materials and equipped; therefore, wastage and spoilage are lessened, and the needs for supervision is reduced.

Ehrhardt, Miller, Freeman and Hom (2011) and Oguntimehin (2001) noted that optimum utilization of Human Resources, development of Human Resources, development of skills of employees, productivity, team spirit, organization culture and climate, quality, healthy work environment, health and safety, morale, image and profitability are major benefit of training to organizational development.

Vidal-Salazar, Hurtado-Torres, Matías-Reche (2012) and Groot, Van den Brink (2000) in separate studies identified that training is one of the most profitable investments an organization can make. The basic steps for an effective training process are establishing a needs analysis, developing training programs and manuals, deliver the training program and evaluate the training program

Ferreira and Leite (2014) stated that the most common types of training are apprentice training, on-the-job training, off-the-job training, vestibule training, classroom training, supervisory training, extension training, audio-visual based training and computer-based training.

Kayode (2001) some common problems in the Nigerian context; Improve the quality of work and raise morale, develop new skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes, use correctly new tools, machines, processes, methods or modifications, reduce waste, accidents, turnover, lateness, absenteeism, and other overhead cost, implement new or changed policies or regulations, fight obsolescence in skills, technologies, methods, products, markets, capital management, bring incumbents to that level of performance which meets the standard of performance for the job. Also develop replacements, prepare people for advancement, improve manpower deployment and ensure continuity of leadership and ensure the survival and growth of the organization.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for the study is human capital theory, Azariadis and Drazen (1990); Pascale and Athos (1981) and Hartog and Brink (2007) expressed that human capital has the possibility of expanding and increasing their capability over time with the required

training and need assessment of the job and specific task. Human capital is inelastic and immeasurable if properly utilized under the right environment, adjusting to specific training and educational development. The return of investment on human capital is complex to calculate since the resources has multiple benefits including bringing creativity and innovation to organizational development that may not be captured in strategic plan and longtime goal.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The survey research design was used in this study. This design was adopted because it entails studying the current state of a unit or group at a particular point in time. The design also entails the use of structured questionnaires to elicit information from the selected sample.

Population of the Study

The population includes all staff of Nigerian Gas Company, Warri. The total staff of the organization in Warri is 511 as at February, 2021.

Sample and Sampling Parameter

The sample is a sub-set of the population which is studied in place of the entire population, because it is difficult to study every element of the study population size. The results of the sample are then generalized to the whole population. We used sample-size calculator to compute for the minimum necessary sample to meet the desired statistical constrained. The sample size derived from online sample calculator is 220 with the following parameters. Confidential level at 95%, margin of error 5%, population, population proportion,

Data Collection

A well-structured questionnaire was designed and administered to 220 respondents captured in the sample size.

Data Presentation

Data were presented in tabular form, so as to facilitate easy comprehension and further analysis of the data. It is chosen because the questionnaire administered is made of closed ended questions which are better presented by tables.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the data for this study, the research adopted the use of sequential statistics by deploying descriptive statistics, correlation and regression to explain the relationship between training and development as well as the influence of training on organizational development. SPSS 23 was used to derive the tables that were analyzed.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

The study examined the relationship between training and organizational development, the influence of training on organization development as well as bidirectional test on both variables. Sequentially, the data derived from the respondents was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study. Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis were engaged to make the findings of the study vigorous.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic Characteristics

From a total of 220 questionnaires administered to respondents in the Nigerian Gas Company in Warri, Delta State, 186 questionnaires were returned and duly filled. This represented 93% response rate which is remarkable to provide generalization of the result derived from the study.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

The demographical characteristics of the respondents identified and discussed nature and characteristics of the respondents as well as define perimeter of relationship, influence and causal direction of various investigated. The summary description of the respondents' age, sex, educational and marital status are hereby presented and interpreted below.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	186	2.63	.789
Sex	186	1.33	.473
Marital_Status	186	1.81	.800
Education_status	186	2.73	.920
Valid N (listwise)	186		

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics in table 1 for the demographic of the respondents showed that the mean value for age, sex, marital status and education status were 2.63, 1.33, 1.81 and 2.73 respectively; this showed a close fluctuation among in the variables serving as parameters to determine the nature and characteristics of the population. This implies that there is a measure of convergence in the population. Main while, the standard deviation for the population for age, marital status and educational status were .789, .800 and .920 respectively. The closeness of these, signified, the respondents shared commonality in preference while for sex, there was divergence.

Table 2 Frequency distribution for age

AGE	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-30	12	6.5	6.5
31-40	68	36.6	43.0
41-50	82	44.1	87.1
51-above	24	12.9	100.0
Total	186	100.0	

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The frequency distribution of table 2 for age among the respondents showed that 18-30 years were 12 representing 6.5%. 31-40, 41-50 and 50-above were 68,82 and 24 representing

36.6%, 44.1% and 12.9% respectively. The bulk of the respondents fell between 31 and 50 years, which readily expressed the respondents matured active respondents in the population. Also the divergence of age also expressed that all segment of the population was fully capture and this is likewise expressed in the comprehensive response of the population.

Table 3 Frequency distribution for Sex

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	124	38.6	66.7	66.7
	Female	62	19.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	186	57.9	100.0	
Total			100.0		

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The frequency distribution in table 3 for sex showed that there were 124 males and 62 females representing 66.7% and 33.3%. This expressed that the organization is male dominated. This can be explained considering majority of the work done in the Nigerian Gas Company are physical effort.

Table 4 Frequency distribution for Marital Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	61	19.0	32.8	32.8
	Married	113	35.2	60.8	93.5
	Divorced	3	.9	1.6	95.2
	Separated	4	1.2	2.2	97.3
	Widow/Widower	5	1.6	2.7	100.0
	Total	186	57.9	100.0	
Total			100.0		

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The frequency distribution in table 4 for marital status were 61, 113 and 3 for single, married and divorced representing 32.8%, 60.8% and 1.6% respectively while for separated and widow/widower categories, the respondents were 4 and 5 representing 2.2% and 2.7% respectively. This implied that the population is diverse and represent all segment of a typical population, this removing the possibility for bias in their preference.

Table 5 Frequency distribution for Education status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SSCE	24	7.5	12.9	12.9
NCE/OND	38	11.8	20.4	33.3
HND/B.Sc.	88	27.4	47.3	80.6
Masters and above	36	11.2	19.4	100.0
Total	186		100.0	
Total		100.0		

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The educational status in table 5 for frequency distribution covered SSCE, NCE/OND, HND/B.Sc., and Masters- above accounting for 24, 38, 88 and 36 respondents representing 12.9%, 20.4%, 47.3 and 19.4 respectively. This implied that the organization is well structured to carry out wide range of tasks that constantly requires training to set the organization on the aspiring path of development. The fact that only 19.4% of its staff have higher degrees is a justification to engage in progressive training.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation deals with the relationship and the strength of relationship between variables under investigation. The correlation in this study is to find out whether the independent variable is related to the dependent variable.

Table 6 Descriptive Statistics for correlation

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
TRAINING	26.5461	3.58478	186
ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT	22.0361	3.89953	186

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The descriptive Statistics in table 6 for the correlation added all the values derived from the questionnaires on each of the variables category and extracted their mean and standard deviation. This summary values will be able to explain if both variables correlated and how they related. In this case, the mean preference for training from the respondents was 26.54 and organizational development was 22.03 while the standard deviation for training and development were 3.58 and 3.89 respectively. This implied that both mean and standard deviation values correlated closely in the same direction.

Table 7 Pearson Correlations

		TRAINING	ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT
TRAINING	Pearson Correlation	1	.383**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	186	186
ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT	Pearson Correlation	.383**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	186	186

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

In table 7, using the 2 tailed Pearson Correlation analysis, the data showed that training is correlated to organizational development at 38% at t-value of 0.0. This therefore indicated that training and organizational development are positively related but the strength of the relation is weak at below 0.50 Or 50%.

Table 8. Spearman Correlations

			TRAINING	ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT
Spearman's rho	TRAINING	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.434**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	186	186
	ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.434**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	186	186

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

In table 8, the nonparametric correlations, using spearman correlation, expressed correlation between training and organizational development at 43% relationship between both variables. Using different correlation techniques utilized for the correlation analysis, the study was able to show that there is a relationship between training and organizational development at t-value of 0.0.

Regression

After knowing the level of relationship from correlation, regression is used to measure the impact or influence of one variable on another variable and also to determine if the relationship between both variable is significant.

Table 9. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10.987	1.985		5.536	.000
TRAININ G	.416	.074	.383	5.618	.000

a. Dependent Variable: ORGANIZATIONAL_DEVELOPMENT
 Source: Authors' Compilation from SPSS (2021).

The regression in table 9 held training constant or as independent variable while expressing its impact on organizational development as dependent variable. The regression result showed that training was able to influence organizational development at 38% and the relationship was significant at t-value of 0.0. Thus the relationship is positive, weak and significant.

Hypotheses Testing

To test our results on the basis of the null hypotheses that were earlier stated, we validate them against the result of the correlation and regression carried out from our study.

Hypothesis 1. There is no relationship between training and organizational development.

Based on the correlation results, the Pearson correlation analysis and Spearman correlation showed that is relationship between the training and organizational development at 38% and 43% respectively. Both analysis showed evidence of relationship between training and development. Thus, we reject the null hypothesis 1.

Hypothesis 2. Training do no impact organizational development.

Based on the regression analysis, the result showed that training was able to influence organizational development by 38% and the relationship was significant at t-value of 0.0. Thus the relationship is positive, weak and significant. We therefore reject the null hypothesis.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations.

The summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations are presented for the study on training and organizational development, a case study of Nigerian Gas Company, Warri, Delta State.

Summary of the findings.

The study on training and organizational development is critical for prioritizing the enhancing human resources capital and its impact on organizational development. The study carried out descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analyses to attain the following.

1. Based on the analysis of descriptive statistics, the mean for training from the respondents was 26.54 and organizational development was 22.03 while the standard deviation for training and development were 3.58 and 3.89 respectively. This implied that both mean and standard deviation values correlated closely in the same direction.
2. Based on the correlation results, the Pearson correlation analysis and Spearman correlation showed that is relationship between the training and organizational development at 38% and 43% respectively. Both analysis showed evidence of relationship between training and development.
3. Based on the regression analysis, the result showed that training was able to influence organizational development by 38% and the relationship was significant at t-value of 0.0. Thus the relationship is positive, weak and significant.

Conclusion

The empirical result derived from the study identified that there is a positive and significant relationship between training and development. However, the study accounted that the strength of the relationship between training and development was weak. As various responses from the respondents indicated, training enabled employees to be aware of organizational goals and trained to improve their capacity to contribute meaningfully in actualizing such goals. Training has positive and significant influence on organizational development in relation to growth in capacity, improved profitability as well as job satisfaction.

Recommendations.

The empirical nature of the study showed that the following recommendation were desirable.

1. There is the need to incorporate incentives into training programme as this will increase the motivation for organization that is strong. Following the weak relationship from the study, it is evidence that mere training without incentives to drive the process was a lagging approach that need to increase the goals of the training programmes.
2. There is the need to provide equal opportunity for all those qualified to attend training programmes. The weak relationship and influence at 38% showed that the training programmes were not sufficient enough to cause the desired results expected to drive the organizational development.
3. There is build synergy between management and employee towards achieving organization goal. The lagging approach to training is not yielding the maximum effort. Relationship need to be strengthened across all categories of the workforce to build trust that is required to reinforce organization development.
4. Organization should accept the responsibility of committing resources aimed at providing training materials and facilities for the staff development.

References

- Armstrong, M. (2012). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. London: Kogan Page.
- Azariadis, C and Drazen, A. (1990). Threshold externalities in economic development. *The Quarterly Journal of Economic*, Vol, 105, Issue 2, 501-525.
- Brown J (2002). Training needs assessment: A must for developing an effective training

- Program. *Public Pers Manag* 31(4):569–578
- Cheung, H and Chan A (2012) Increasing the competitive positions of countries through Employee training. *Int J Manpower* 33(2):144–158
- Cole, G.A. (2002) *Personnel and human resource management*. 5th Edition, London: Continuum Publisher.
- Ehrhardt, K, Miller, J, Freeman, S and Hom P (2011) An examination of the relationship between training comprehensiveness and organizational commitment: further exploration of training perceptions and employee attitudes. *Hum Resource Dev Q* 22(4):459–489
- Ferreira A and Leite R (2014). A glimpse at the Portuguese employees' perceptions of training and development: what they get is what they see? *Int J Appl Manag Sci Eng* 1(1):1–16
- Groot W, Van den Brink H (2000) Education, training and employability. *Appl Econ* 32: 573–581
- Hartog and Brink (2007). *Human capital. Advances in theory and evidence*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Isyaku, LA. (2000), "Training and Retraining of Teachers through Distance Education". Being a paper presented at the National Workshop on Distance Education Held at Abuja Nigeria.
- Kayode, T (2001). The Role of Training in Personnel Management. *Journal of the Institute of Personnel Management of Nigeria*. Vol. 10, No 7
- Latif, K (2012). An integrated model of training effectiveness and satisfaction with employee Development interventions. *Ind Commer Train* 44(4):211–222
- Mathews B, Ueno A, Kekale T, Repka M, Pereira Z, Silva G (2001) Quality training: needs And evaluation—ndings from a European survey. *Total Qual Manag* 12(4):483–490
- Noe R, Tews M (2008). Strategic training and development. In: Storey J, Wright PM, Ulrich D (eds) *The Routledge companion to strategic human resource management*. Routledge, pp 262–284
- Noe R (2010) *Employee training and development*. McGraw-Hill, New York
- Oribabor, P.E. (2000). Human Resources Management, A Strategic Approval. *Human Resources Management* 9 (4) 21 - 24
- Tharenou P (2010) Training and development in organizations. In: Wilkinson A, Bacon N, Redman T, Snell S (eds) *The sage handbook of human resource management*. Sage, London, pp 155–172
- Thomason, G. (2001), *A Textbook of Personnel Management*. London, Institute of Personnel Management.
- Ubeda-García M, Marco-Lajara D, Sabater-Sempere V, García-Lillo F (2013). Does training Influence organizational performance? Analysis of the Spanish hotel sector. *European Journal Training Development*. 37(4):380–413
- Vidal-Salazar M, Hurtado-Torres N, Matías-Reche F (2012). Training as a generator of employee capabilities. *Int J Hum Resour Manage* 23(13):2680–2697